

A proposal for large scale electricity generation from high pressure applications using piezoelectric materials

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Abstract - At present, a great deal of research effort has been directed to finding eco-friendly and renewable sources of energy. With the rising costs of crude oil and petroleum, along with the derogatory effects that they pose to the environment, this sort of approach is of utmost importance. This has also led to the search for alternate methods of transforming the various forms of energy into electrical form. Popular renewable energy sources such as hydropower, solar power and wind power require massive financial investments, give comparatively much lower power output, and have a low scale of efficiency. Nuclear power offers a cleaner source of energy, however, the cost involved in the setting up of nuclear power plants and its subsequent maintenance, along with the accompanying international political uproar involved outweigh its benefits. In recent years, there has been growing interest in harnessing the power of mechanical vibrations and pressure to generate electricity. Piezoelectric materials are by far, one of the most efficient transducer elements to accomplish this task. Over the last decade many piezoelectric elements, both natural and artificial, have been found. They have, however, been mostly used for applications with a low power generation, in the range of μW to mW . This paper presents a suggestion to expand the field of piezoelectricity generation to other areas for large scale electrical power generation. Many other methods are possible, and some of the promising ones are mentioned in this paper.

Keywords-piezoelectricity, PZT cantilever beam; stacked structure; high pressure; piezoelectric generators

I. INTRODUCTION

Piezoelectricity refers to the ability of a material to produce a charge separation along its surface upon application of mechanical strain. A type of dipole is created in the material and this results in a potential difference across its ends. The piezoelectric effect is the linear electromechanical interaction between the mechanical and the electrical state in crystalline

materials with no inversion symmetry [1]. It is a reversible process in that materials exhibiting the direct piezoelectric effect, which is the internal generation of electrical charge resulting from an applied mechanical force, can also exhibit the converse piezoelectric effect, which is the internal generation of a mechanical force resulting from an applied electrical field. The process of piezoelectric effect takes place in piezoelectric materials when they are compressed along certain axes producing a measurable voltage on the surface of the material. A charge arises when the materials, which have no axis of symmetry, are strained: the center of the positive charge in the lattice is slightly separated from the center of negative charge, and that creates an electric field, which can be measured on opposite faces of the material. Similarly, upon application of an electric field across the faces induces the ions to be mobile, thereby deforming the crystal. This makes piezoelectric materials very useful for a variety of functions. A very small amount of deformation applied to piezoelectric materials can create a measurable voltage, and this makes piezoelectric materials efficient as electromechanical transducers [2]. Fig. 1 below shows a simplified graphical description of the mechanism of piezoelectricity.

Figure 1: Simplified demonstration of the piezoelectric effect
 Piezoelectric materials are generally utilized for applications where there is a low power requirement. They include portable electronic devices such as mp3 players, mobile phones, GPS receivers or sensors of remote sensing systems or transmitters which are conventionally powered by batteries. The amount of pressure required for distortion of a piezoelectric ceramic element by 0.05mm can generate nearly 100 kV, however the electric current generated is of the order of mA to μ A. Key factors involved in the amount of energy produced by a piezoelectric material have to do with the stress on the element, that is the ratio of the applied force to the surface area of the element. When the composition of the ceramic, the volume of the ceramic element, and the applied force are constant, the element that has the smallest surface area will generate the most electrical energy. Very high amounts of electric energy are obtainable with piezoelectric elements when the amount of stress applied to it is very high or very frequent. For example, a 2 kN force properly applied to a cubic-centimeter sized quartz crystal produces over 12.5 kV [3]. The amount of energy will increase linearly with the amount of stress applied to it, so the more pressure there is on the piezoelectric material, the more power will be generated. With this vision, many individual researchers and corporations have started working in this field. The most notable of recent projects undertaken are of the Israeli company Innovattech Energy Harvesting Systems, which has placed piezoelectric generators in certain roads in Israeli cities to harvest mechanical energy imparted to roadways from passing vehicles [4]. This paper suggests other potential scenarios for large scale electricity generation from piezoelectricity, namely in airport runways and railway tracks. Other scenarios, although possible are not mentioned in this paper, due to space constraints here. Before a proposal for electricity generation can be presented, it is necessary to give a mathematical model for the calculation of power output from piezoelectric materials.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELS OF THE PIEZOELECTRIC MATERIALS

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of a piezoelectric cantilever beam

The three mathematical models presented below are most frequently used to model power generation from piezoelectric materials [5]. It should be stressed, however, that these models are for the general small scale applications, and is based on the model of a bimorph piezoelectric cantilever beam. With the proper modifications, they can be utilized for large scale measurements. Those modifications are beyond the scope of this paper, and only certain scenarios are presented here. Fig. 2 below shows the schematic diagram of a piezoelectric cantilever beam.

A. Electrical equivalent circuit

The study of the transient dynamic characteristics of a PZT (piezoelectric materials) bender utilizing electrical equivalent models has been performed in previous studies and the model has shown fair accuracy in various conditions of mechanical stress. Fig. 3 shows an electric equivalent circuit model for a PZT beam.

Figure 3: Circuit representation of a PZT beam

Here a voltage source is connected in series with an inductor, a resistor and a capacitor that build a resonant circuit. The transformer represents the voltage adaptation while the capacitor indicates the inherent capacitance of the device. The circuit can be described by using Kirchhoff's voltage law:

$$\sigma_{in} = L_m \dot{\epsilon} + R_b \ddot{\epsilon} + \frac{\ddot{\epsilon}}{C_k} + nV \quad (1)$$

$$i = C_k \dot{V} \quad (2)$$

The equivalent circuits leads to the correlation between the strain ϵ and voltage V :

$$\ddot{\epsilon} = - \frac{Y}{k_1 k_2 m} \epsilon - \frac{b_m}{k_1 m} \dot{\epsilon} + \frac{Y}{k_1 k_2 m} \frac{d_{21}}{2t_C} V + \frac{\ddot{y}}{k_2} \quad (3)$$

and

$$V = \frac{n_p t_c d_{31} Y}{\epsilon} \dot{\epsilon} \quad (4)$$

where ϵ , $\dot{\epsilon}$ second and first time derivatives of strain.

B. Beam theory (Timoshenko and Euler–Bernoulli)

The static analysis of a piezoelectric cantilever sensor is typically performed by the use of calculations employed for deflection of a thermal bimorph proposed by Timoshenko. The principle is based on the strain compatibility between three cantilever beams joined along the bending axis. Due to forces applied by one or all of the layers, the deflection of the three layer structure is derived from a static equilibrium state. The structure considered is a piezoelectric heterogeneous bimorph, where two piezoelectric layers are bonded on both sides of a purely elastic layer, i.e. brass.

Figure. 4: a basic geometry of the three-layer multimorph.

Brass with a pure elasticity is sandwiched between the upper and lower layers of the PZT material. The modeling of this structure neglects shear effects and ignores residual stress induced curvature. In addition, the beam thickness is much less than the piezoelectric-induced curvature, so the second-order effects such as electrostriction can be ignored. Moreover, the radius of curvature for all the layers is assumed to be approximately the same to those of the structure, simply because of the assumption that the thickness is much less than the overall beam curvature.

The total strain at the surface of each layer is the sum of the strains caused by the piezoelectric effect, the axial force, and the bending. It is noted that the sign of the surface strain depends on the bending of either the top or bottom surface of the layer:

$$\epsilon_i = \epsilon_{piezo} + \epsilon_{axial} + \epsilon_{bend} = d_{31} E_i + \frac{Ft}{A_i Y_i} \pm \frac{t_i}{2r} \quad (5)$$

where ϵ_{piezo} in the linear constitutive equation above considers the transverse piezoelectric coupling coefficient d_{31} and the electric field across the thickness of the layer E_i for a piezoelectric material, t_1 and t_3 are the thickness of the PZT layer and t_2 is the thickness of the center shim, A_i is the area of the corresponding layer and Y_i is the Young's modulus of elasticity.

Hence the radius of curvature is given by the term:

$$\frac{1}{r} = \frac{2d_{31}DA^{-1}C}{2 - DA^{-1}B} \quad (6)$$

where $A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -1 & 0 \\ A_1 Y_1 & A_2 Y_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$, $B = \begin{bmatrix} t_1 + t_2 \\ t_2 + t_3 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$,

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} -E \\ E \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

On the other hand, Euler–Bernoulli beam theory describes the relationship between the radius of curvature and the force applied, which is given by the following equation:

$$\rho A \frac{\partial^4 w(x,t)}{\partial t^4} + Y I \frac{\partial^4 w(x,t)}{\partial x^4} = F(t) \quad (7)$$

Where ρ is the density, I is the moment of inertia and $F(t)$ is the applied force. A general solution for this equation is given by:

$$w(x, t) = \sum q_i(t)X_i(x) \quad (8)$$

Where the displacement and the vibration is expressed in the case of a cantilever beam as follows:

$$X_i(x) = \cosh(\beta_i x) - \cos(\beta_i x) - \frac{\sinh(\beta_i L) - \sin(\beta_i L)}{\cosh(\beta_i L) + \cos(\beta_i L)} \times (\sinh(\beta_i x) - \sin(\beta_i x)) \quad (9)$$

and

$$q_i(t) = \frac{1}{\omega_{di}} e^{-\zeta \omega_n t} \int_0^t F_i(\tau) e^{-\zeta \omega_n \tau} \sin(\omega_{di}(t - \tau)) d\tau \quad (10)$$

$$\beta_i^4 = \frac{\omega_n^4}{c^2} \quad (11)$$

ω_n is the natural frequency obtained by solving the transcendental equation:

$$\cosh(\beta_i L) \cos(\beta_i L) + 1 = 0 \quad (12)$$

The radius of curvature is given by the following equations:

$$r = \frac{1}{2w(L)} L^2, \text{ where } \frac{1}{r} = \dot{\omega}(x) \text{ and } \omega(x) = \frac{1}{2v} x^2$$

Hence by substituting the radius of curvature term in equation (6), the voltage produced for the PZT bender is given by:

$$V = \frac{2w(L) \epsilon p}{L^2} \frac{2-D\Lambda^{-1}z}{2d_{31}D\Lambda^{-1}} \begin{bmatrix} -1 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

C. Conservation of energy

The principle is based on the fact that the total energy of the PZT bender stored is equal to the sum of the mechanical energy applied to the beam and the electrical energy on the charges being applied by the electric field. When a mechanical stress is applied, the energy stored in a PZT layer is the sum of the mechanical energy and the electric-field-induced energy. Thus, the energy stored in a PZT layer is expressed as follows:

$$U_u = \frac{1}{2}(s_{11}^E \sigma_1^2 - d_{31}^2 E_3^2) \sigma_1 = \frac{1}{2} s_{11}^E \sigma_1^2 \quad (14)$$

where σ is the stress and s is the stiffness matrix.

On the other hand, the energy in the metal layer can be expressed by a simple equation because of the lack of the electric field as follows:

$$U_m = \frac{1}{2} s_m \sigma_1^2 \quad (15)$$

The total energy of the beam is given as:

$$U_{total} = \int_0^L \int_0^W \left(\int_{\frac{t_2}{2}}^{\frac{t_2}{2}+t_1} dU_u dz + \int_{\frac{t_2}{2}}^{\frac{t_2}{2}} dU_m dz + \int_{\frac{t_2}{2}}^{-\frac{t_2}{2}} dU_l dz \right) dy dx \quad (16)$$

On the other hand, the electric field is given by $E = \frac{V}{2t_2}$. The total electrical energy is equal to a product of the charge and the voltage. Thus, the charge generated in the beam is obtained by a partial derivative of the total energy with respect to the voltage:

$$Q = \frac{\partial U_{total}}{\partial V} = -3 \frac{d_{31} s_m (t_2 + t_3) L^2}{x} F_o \quad (17)$$

The capacitance of the piezoelectric material is described as the relation between the voltage and charge on the piezoelectric material. Hence the capacitance C_{free} of the beam can be found, where no load is applied:

$$C_{free} = \frac{v_{33}^T W L 2 t_3}{2 t_2} \left(1 + \left(\frac{6 s_m t_2 (t_2 + t_3)^2 - x}{x} \right) K_{31}^2 \right) \quad (18)$$

where K_{31} is the coupling coefficient. Thus, the voltage generated is found as a function of the applied force:

$$V = \frac{Q}{C_{free}} = - \frac{6 d_{31} s_m t_2 (t_2 + t_3) L}{v_{33}^T W x \left(1 + \left(\frac{6 s_m t_2 (t_2 + t_3)^2}{x} - 1 \right) K_{31}^2 \right)} F_o \quad (19)$$

III. POTENTIAL SCENARIOS FOR LARGE-SCALE GENERATION OF ELECTRICAL POWER

The potential scenarios for large-scale piezoelectricity generation would inevitably be in cases where there is a frequent application of huge pressure. These conditions are met in places where there are large groups of people commuting or where there is a high frequency of vehicular movement. Therefore, the most common examples are railroad tracks, airport runways, roads, highways and footpaths. Fig. 5 shows the type of setup required for power generation.

Figure 5: Piezoelectric generators for different power generation scenarios

A. Roads and highways

Traffic at roads and highways varies throughout the day, with more traffic during the day than at night, and in certain time durations throughout the day. An average figure is required of the number of vehicles passing through a certain point, for a certain time period such as an hour, in order to calculate the total pressure exerted by moving vehicles on the road surface. Recent experimentations carried out by Innowattech in Israel, consists of putting IPEG (Innowattech Piezoelectric Electric Generators) 6cm under the road level and at a distance of 30cm apart, the piezoelectric system being covered by a layer of asphalt. From these trials, it has been seen that a truck weighing at around 5 tons can generate 2000 V, and a 1 km stretch of generators along a dual carriageway (assuming 600 vehicles go through that road segment in an hour), can generate about 400 kWh, enough energy to power 600-800

homes. An estimate of the number of roads in Israel can help deduce the total energy that can be attained from Innovattech's proposed method.

B. Airport runways

When an aircraft takes off or lands, a massive amount of pressure is exerted on the runway, which is equivalent to the take-off weight of the aircraft. The huge amount of mechanical energy involved can be converted by placing an arrangement of piezoelectric materials at a certain distance below the runway. This arrangement will act as a form of piezoelectric generator, and the efficiency can be increased with a stacked structure, which consists of many layers of piezoelectric materials and are suitable for handling a large force and collecting a huge amount of charge. In the commercial aircraft business, the two leading brands are the Airbus and Boeing, with the most flown models being the Airbus 380 (A380) and the Boeing 787. The maximum takeoff weight for the A380 [6] is 560 tonnes (560,000 kilograms) and that of the 787 is 502,500 pounds (227,930 kilograms) [7]. Taking into account the number of aircraft landing or taking off, the world's busiest airport [8] from statistical data gathered in 2010 is Hartsfield-Jackson Atlanta International Airport in Atlanta, Georgia, United States, with an average of 109 landings or takeoffs every hour. The amount of voltage generated from a single A380 would be approximately 224 kV, and about 8,138 kWh energy could be produced which will be sufficient for powering 12,207-16,276 homes.

C. Footpaths and pedestrian walks

In crowded spots, energy can be generated from the motion of people. A sustainable way to harness energy from everyday movements such as walking on a sidewalk, moving through a subway or train turnstile or dancing on a dance floor is possible using piezoelectric materials. The concepts focus on large numbers of people moving in dense areas to step on tiles embedded in the floor which would use piezoelectric materials to generate electricity that could be captured and used. About 3-6 watts per step can be converted. The Victoria train station in London has 34,000 people walking through in one rush hour period. Many kilowatts of energy could be harvested and put back into low-power circuits and equipment. This could include audio equipment, display screens, or about 6.5 million LED lights. With higher number of people, more power can be generated and this can also be used large-scale generation [9].

D. Railroad tracks

A huge amount of pressure is exerted by trains on the railroad tracks, which would provide a large quantity of energy if harnessed. Pads of piezoelectric materials placed at the juncture where wheels make contact tracks would receive the high pressure. The structure of the pads should be stacked in

order that a large force is tolerated and a greater amount of charge is stored.

IV. CONCLUSION

The recent emphasis on eco-friendly sources of energy has opened new horizons for the global energy market. Piezoelectricity offers a viable alternative to conventional fossil fuels. It is relatively inexpensive and easy to install, and recycles otherwise wasteful forms of energy. However, it should be mentioned that the scenarios presented here are an approximation, and current experiments have shown that although large amounts of energy can be generated, the full amount cannot be used. The efficiency is low, in the range of twenty to thirty percent. Further work in this field is required to find out more efficient methods of utilization.

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